

Design of Emotional Web Interface Using InSite Factors

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Abstract

This paper presents an approach to improving the hedonic qualities of web interfaces based on the principles of emotional design. A computational model of emotional web is formulated for the construction of a system which dynamically responds to the emotion changes of users after an analysis of their inputs to the system and the way in which they browse the contents. By adapting the interface with predefined patterns of emotional transition, the system is expected to stimulate the users and increase their positive emotion by giving cognitive support. A list of the elements of interface that may affect emotion are described and evaluated.

Keywords: emotional interface, InSite factors, OutSite factors

1. Introduction

In recent years emotion has become an important issue for design as a transition from useful, usable and satisfying design to affective, efficient and satisfying design. It is well known that positive emotion affects the memory, motivation and attachment. Because of these reasons managing the emotional interaction between human and computer has been a question for interface designers. This question related to psychology theories of supporting users with emotion.

The cognitive theory of emotion developed by Ortony, Clore and Collins (1988) defines emotion as “valenced” (positive or negative) reactions to situations consisting of events, actors and objects. Further more, the valance of emotion depends on the desirability of the situation and one’s goals and preferences. Rolls (2002) defines emotion as states elicited by rewards and punishments, including changes in rewards and punishments. A reward is anything that an animal will seek and will do something to get; a punishment is something that an animal will work to escape or avoid. In a design context users may try to avoid errors in work process, unwanted noise, spam or frustrating content. An example of unwanted interaction in interfaces is when the interface is too confusing to use.

In our research by understanding the causes and effects of emotions we aim to find out the standards of emotional interaction and represent them in a computational model. We studied the possible elements in a web site that might have impacts on user’s emotion. For this purpose we carried out a qualitative research to validate our emotional interaction model. The findings were demonstrated in a storytelling system. Qualitative research is useful when the outcome of the research is not clear and when there is a need to define new variables.

Our implementation is based on a model of emotional interaction that uses the user’s profile characteristics to adapt the design elements of an interface. To enable a web interface to respond in a positive and affective way, the system needs to have two basic abilities (Picard, 1997):

- Making a belief of the user’s emotion,
- Responding appropriately according to that belief.

In Tzvetanova and Tang (2005) we have proposed an interactive method for recognition of the user's emotional state. This method uses the environment, psychology and task factors related to the user and we call them OutSite factors (outside the web site). The InSite factors (factors inside the web site that might influence the user's emotion) will be evaluated below. The model of the InSite elements represents dynamical changes of the interface based on the principles of: graphic design, cinema emotional approaches and the theory of semiotics. In addition we carried out a qualitative research on the InSite elements with Asian experts by analyzing the existing design approaches to storytelling and emotional web pages. The outcomes of the research are scenarios of emotional interaction that can be applied to emotional interface design.

2. Review of relevant research

A model of the InSite factors was defined to explain computationally case studies and relate them to a web interface. In other words this model is a list of elements of a web interface structure that may influence the user's emotion. We have collected these elements from previous research on human-computer-interaction and web design principles (Nielsen 1999; Shneiderman and Plaisant 2005).

The model is shown in Figure 1. It has two main branches: content and design. The content is related to the subject domain including text information, visual information (such as diagrams, tables, illustrations, etc.), tactile information and acoustic information. In addition to visual aspects, such as colours and shapes, the exploration of the sensuous aspects of design can enhance emotional characteristics of the information transferred. Haptics can also facilitate new creativity in interaction design and bring pleasant experiences to users about a product (Hara 2005). Kenya Hara (2005) believes that the human senses are unexplored areas for information transformation between products and human. The haptic information that the user may perceive in an interface is via touching, hearing and visioning. Egmond, Desmet and Helm (2004) conducted experiments on the relation of sound with the basic emotions and they believed that sound can be a tool for emotional design. The usual case is that the users have the equipment only for hearing and visioning such as the screens and speakers or headphones.

The **design** branch is the listing of aesthetic and functional features of a web site. Looking at the organization the first branch is about how to present the content. Relating to this issue, there are many studies which indicate that *mnemonics* can affect usability and emotions like frustration, confidence or anger (Shneiderman and Plaisant 2005); *Navigation* may also affect the visitors by confusing/assuring them (Jacko, 2003). Furthermore the accurate *mnemonics* create confidence in the efficiency of the system. *Presentation* is also related to usability, i.e., the pleasant feature of a product derives from the factor that it is easy and comfortable to use. The *general appeal* is related to the first impression, as well as the contours of the user graphic interface, that give that first impression. The *silhouette* can provoke the first reactions and lead to a rise in the interest, joy or even happiness in seeing something that is liked. In design it is well known that the *composition* can influence emotions, such as symmetric composition represents harmony and beauty. Furthermore *colors* are also linked to emotional interaction (D'Andrade and Egan 1974). Ou, Luo, Woodcock and Wright (2004) have evaluated the links between single colors and emotions and defined ten sensational perceptions of colors: warm-cool, heavy-light, modern-classical, clean-dirty, active-passive, hard-soft, tense-relaxed, fresh-stale, masculine-feminine, and like-dislike. Furthermore they (2004b) have also evaluated the sensation of pairs of colors. *Color schemes* have a role in typography in terms of readability. Their research shows that students tend to prefer more dynamic interfaces with animation and video than others with such features, because video clips are entertaining and contain visual and acoustic information.

Figure 1: InSite branching hierarchy tree, which lists the components in an assembly inside the web site factors that might have impacts on user's emotion

It is considered that usability and emotion are related. According to the OCC model an object can be blamed for their malfunctioning as a consequence of actions of the object as an agent. Researchers made usability testing and observed the emotional responses from

web interfaces. Kim and Moon (1998) made a selection of a comprehensive set of emotive scales for measuring the emotions elicited by cyber interfaces. By the examination of the subjects they have defined the following interface elements as most memorable to the subjects: format, graphics, position, size, content, motion, color tone, main color, brightness, symmetry. Loraine Justice (1999) has demonstrated that *motion* can increase the efficiency and affect in ITS.

3. Interviews

In this research interviews were conducted with design experts to find out the patterns in emotional responses to interfaces and the connection between interface design elements and emotional responses to them. These interviews are one-to-one encounters in which the interviewer follows a semi-structured set of issues/topics to guide the discussion. The objective of the qualitative research was to explore and uncover deep-seated emotions, motivations and attitudes. Interviews are most often employed when dealing with sensitive matters and respondents are likely to give evasive or even misleading answers when directly questioned. The interviews were conducted with 20 Asian designers, 8 of them in the product design field and 12 of them are interface and graphic design experts. The sessions were video recorded, which was useful later for analysing the data in detail such as facial expressions, gestures and time of the day. The research was carried out with the experts in the fields because they can describe design patterns and they have experience in conveying emotions in their own projects. This qualitative research is intended to observe the already existing practices for emotional web design with detailed explanation by the users and designers themselves, who may not have explicitly thought of the issues in an emotional approach to interface design and applications.

First, over 60 web sites that we considered conveying emotions in some degrees were gathered. For the interviews, we selected 6 web sites related to positive emotion and 6 related to negative emotion, as shown in Figure 2. The positive web sites were selected on two criteria: by subject and by appearance relating to positive emotion. These sites all have positive emotions topics. The negative web sites were selected on the same criteria which were related to negative emotion or trying to convey negative emotion via the interface or via the content. The examples that were shown to the interviewees were:

Positive emotion:

- <http://www.dbtoons.com/> - funny cartoons,
- <http://www.happiness-records.com/> - music record company that named themselves happiness,
- <http://www.butlerwebs.com/inspiration/happiness.htm> - web page that inspires and motivates,
- <http://www.billrettberg.com/> - positive images from special celebrations,
- <http://www.time.com/time/2005/happiness/> - online issue of Time magazine dedicated to happiness,
- <http://www.rthk.org.hk/elearning/dessert/game.htm> - entertaining and learning cute Hong Kong web site.

Negative emotion:

- <http://www.angryflower.com/> - personal web page of a teenager, who is angry,
- <http://www.metallica.com/index.asp> - an aggressive hard sound music group,
- <http://www.antitdegames.com/movies/view.php?id=15&t=movies> – violent flash movies and games,
- <http://pdl.warnerbros.com/wbmovies/corpsebride/flashsite/main.html> - a sad cartoon movie home site talking about death and sadness,
- <http://www.abc.net.au/health/depression/quiz.htm> - a depression related web page,
- <http://spartantheme.warnerbros.com/> - a site of a violent action movie.

Positive Emotions Related Interfaces

Negative Emotions Related Interfaces

Figure 2: Visual impressions of the positive and negative web sites used in the interviews

The interviews had predefined questions but informal characters, as shown in Figure 3. In the beginning, the research model was introduced to the interviewees, and was explained to them that the interviews were conducted in order to verify whether those elements existed and what the prescriptions were that could be concluded for emotional design. The experts

were asked about their preferences on web sites, the emotional elements of these web sites, and the design patterns in conveying emotion via interfaces. The average duration of an interview was half an hour to forty minutes.

Figure 3: Designers explaining ideas at the interviews

4. Results

“Affect” has many implications on the design of products and software. Variables related to affect such as engagement and entertainment were not observed in this study. The study attempted to cover only emotional reactions either positive or negative. In the interviews it was difficult to separate usability factors from emotional factors.

The structure of the interviews and the examples were prepared to facilitate the designers in explaining the emotional interaction in the presented web sites. The interviews were analyzed for the ideas on design of emotion. Selected scenarios from the interviews are presented in Figures 4 and 5. InSite elements that the experts agreed the most on are shown in the data structure summary. The recommendations of the experts for positive emotion design are positioned at the end of these elements with descriptive words.

The subjects believed that the initial attraction to the interface was important for the users to get interested in the *content*. The silhouette was the first visual impression of a web site that can help people to decide whether could find useful or interesting information on the given page. The interviewees considered that the users might look initially for certain *contents*. The essential element for attracting the attention of a user is to understand the correct style and the message conveyed with the interface.

One of the interviewees commented on one of the web sites by saying: “This one is not nice, it is hospital-like”. In the interviews, most of the designers described not really an emotion, but rather a style that is relating to emotional appearance. The interview results showed that there existed an expectation on the appearance of a web site that matches the *content* or invites the users to explore more. On the average, the interviews indicated that the *text information* should be innovative, exciting and useful. The *visual information* should be related to the topics or helpful for understanding the topics. Pictures were reported to be one of the most powerful tools for conveying emotions. All the interviewees believed that images led to certain feelings. In particular, Asian users related colorful images to happiness. The respondents also believed that the *audio information* can transmit emotions. Many of the interviewees agreed that background music could enhance emotional appearance.

Regarding the *design* of an emotional web site, it was suggested that *quality* also could elicit positive emotions. It was described the quality as a detailed careful design of an interface, which can keep users attracted and fascinated by its appearance, thus helps to explore the contents with other functional support of the web site. As motioned before *graphics* have emotional properties. In detail they should have the quality via legibility. In terms of the *graphic's attractiveness* animation can be added, the experts discussed. In the case when the *graphics* are static: natural images can give a feeling of relaxation. For instance happinessrecord.com has “spring like” images to convey a feeling of happiness. This web site uses mainly natural *materials* such as images of wood, grass and flowers.

In terms of interaction, two major concepts emerged in the interviews: ease of use and exploration. When the users have difficulty in their task performance they may get disappointed or frustrated. The second variable, exploration makes people expect something to happen and get attracted to the experience of interacting with the system. An interviewee commented: “People like the fact that what they expected are actually happening as they go on with browsing a web”. Some of the web sites which are in the negative emotion category were described as unnecessarily sad or miserable, but still with something mystical. The web site called Corpse Bride has a sad story showing sad love, most of the interviewees found this web site attractive for exploring because it is nicely done and explorative.

A conclusion that we can draw from the interviews is that design elements are indirectly related to emotional appraisal. However they cannot influence the user in a major way. The topic/content presented is considered the most emotionally related item, and the design elements can enhance the experience of getting the contents.

In this section the observations from the qualitative research were summarized. In the next section, a design implementation based on the findings will be described. The application scenario has been developed in order to demonstrate the design guidelines for emotion as explained earlier in this paper by the formulation of InSite and OutSite factors.

Content	
Text Information	
<u>Exiting, Useful, Innovative</u>	The users like exiting content, that gives them rich information. Usually they search for a particular information and when they find a web site that match their expectation they are satisfied. The information can act as agent when it is facilitating a completion of a task or as an event when the information meets their desires.
Visual Information	
<u>Related, Exiting, Colourful</u>	The visual information was reported as the most powerful tool for emotional appearance in interfaces. Visual acts as an object and have informative usability properties.
Acoustic Information	
<u>Guiding</u>	Acoustic information can act as an agent when eliciting positive experiences. Furthermore as an agent can be guiding and transfer information. Sound relates to hearing sense.

Figure 4: Description of the content design scenarios for elements related to the emotion summarized from the interviews presented as a data structure summary.

Design	
Organisation - Mnemonics	
Readability → <u>Clear</u>	In terms of perceiving the system as an agent, a usability suggestion is to have clear readability and understandable layout.
Colour → Scheme → <u>Light, Warm</u>	Colour elicits emotion as an agent, and colour is a property for sentiment associations.
Graphics → Legibility → <u>Quality</u>	Quality is conveying emotions as an object and as an event, because it is increasing the expectation of the users. Quality has many properties such as visual, interactive, usability and content correctness.
Graphics → Attractiveness → Dynamic → <u>Animated</u>	Animated interfaces are acting as an agent to facilitate understanding of the topic and increase enjoyment.
Graphics → Attractiveness → Static → <u>Natural</u>	Graphics of nature can act as an object or an event. User can contemplate a nice view or dream looking at the nature of a sunny island with blue sky and pure water.
Organisation → Surface	
<u>Experiential</u>	A visual of a surface elicits memories of haptics properties and can elicit emotions as an event when acts as a memory elicitor or an object when contemplating the visual.
Organisation → Material	
<u>Natural</u>	Natural materials can be perceived as an event, and they may bring memories of nature.
Organisation → Sound	
Service → Background → <u>Guiding</u>	The background music can act as an agent and elicit positive experience and can be guiding and informative. Sound relates to hearing sense.
HCI → Interactivity	
Recognition → <u>Explorative, Easy</u>	Usability is eliciting emotions as an agent facilitating the interaction and enhancing the hedonistic characteristics via explorative and easy interaction.

Figure 5: Description of the design elements scenarios related to emotion summarized from the interviews presented as data structure summary

4. Implementation of the InSite Factors for Interface Adaptation

We are demonstrating one scenario based on the research into an emotionally adaptive storytelling system. The implementation involves a Tibet story for Asian users who like to know more about minority cultures in China. In online storytelling the user perceives the presentation of a story via going through an experience of the content. In our implementation the content is presented with text that people read through. The system is making an assumption that a user's emotion is related to the interaction style of the media (Tzvetanova and Tang 2005). We made scenarios for emotional interaction based on the interviews as case studies. We interpreted those scenarios to the system in a rule-based form. The application of the rules depends on the assumed emotion. These rules are rated according to

their importance to the effective emotional interaction. For instance the system assumes by reasoning the interaction style that the user is bored. For boredom, the main reaction from the system is to display exiting images. If the boredom persists, then the interface will add motion, otherwise, it will stay static. We have used the OutSite factors and the InSite factors pools to create various scenarios for emotional interactions. A multiple input (event) from the user into the system is taken to make a belief about the emotional state or possible emotional arousal. Once the system gets an *input* (an event) from the user it passes it to the reasoning *machine of the state* that makes an enquiry to the *OutSite Factors rules pool* which has a descriptive model of the possible events and rules about them. The belief about the emotion is passed to the *reasoning machine for emotional response* that refers to the *InSite pool* of the rules. The InSite factors presented earlier consist of rules we took from the literature, such as semantics and aesthetic preferences. We have evaluated those observations that describe the rules about user's preferences for interface design related to emotions. After an appropriate response is selected from the InSite pool an output response is displayed. A visual image of the interface change is shown in Figure 6.

In details for illustrating the story we have chosen natural feeling photos as suggested in the interviews. Like in the cinematography, metaphorically some of the most emotional sciences are animated in order to enhance the intensity of emotion. A form has something to do with people's perceiving emotion as an object, by looking and contemplating the shape and the material. It is argued that usability can oppose emotional design. On contrary functionality can elicit emotion when people perceive a situation as an event or an agent. Developing an appropriate design is by testing. That is, developing an early prototype and then watching how people are trying to use it. We have tried to make this implementation this way in order to demonstrate and evaluate further our model for adaptation to user's emotion by using the suggested design elements derived from our studies on the InSite and OutSite factors.

Figure 6: Visual impressions of the same interface with and without images

5. Conclusions

In this research project we have taken a symbolic approach to improving the effectiveness of web interface by adding an emotional response system to a web interface design based on a simple list of emotional elements. In this implementation we did not include many functional elements and we have focused mainly on the appearance. We will try to develop more rules in the future and validate the findings by evaluating this implementation. The implementation is to be evaluated with users in comparison with two other versions. The process for adapting web interfaces to user emotions involves design, evaluation, and redesign. Still some InSite factors responses have to be enhanced in the system, such as motion, sound and interactivity.

6. Acknowledgments

This research aims at adding a new dimension to the existing research projects in the Design Technology Research Centre in the School of Design of the Hong Kong Polytechnic University, which are still largely based on digital and computational models, whose inference control mechanisms are not based on human cognition, rather, they are based on symbolic models of mathematic and mechanic thinking. This research is supported by a PhD studentship from the Hong Kong Polytechnic University.

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